

Building A Spoken-reference Achievement Test Using the Item Response Theory in the Psychometric Course According to Three-parameters Logistic Model

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to build a spoken-reference achievement test using the item response theory in the psychometric course according to the logarithmic three-parameter model, the test included (36) items of the multiple-choice type with four alternatives. The test was applied to the study sample, whose number is (115) male and female students at Al-Isra University. The results of the study reached the fulfilment of the assumptions of the item response theory in the study data, matching the responses of (34) test items to the assumptions of the 3-parameter logarithmic model and deleting (two items) that did not match the model, the results of the assessments of the parameters of the items (difficulty, discrimination, and estimation) showed that they were acceptable within the criteria mentioned in the literature of educational and psychological measurement and evaluation.

Introduction

University education aspires to create a generation of learners who possess knowledge, skills, values and experiences and to benefit from these skills and knowledge to employ them and discover new applications that touch its natural reality in society, especially students of the Department of Psychology, who will be a new boom that changes the local labour market.

The educational psychometric process relies on tools and measures that provide quantitative data that allow educators to accurately understand educational phenomena, in order to know the extent to which the educational goals are achieved and the students' achievement level, the achievement tests were prepared as an essential and important part of the educational process. Through the various types and forms of tests, the database on which we rely to make decisions and reveal the strengths and weaknesses of students is obtained to be able to classify them.

The benchmark tests are used to assess an individual's performance in relation to a criterion, or a predetermined level of performance, without the need to compare his performance with that of his colleagues, in the sense that these tests measure levels that can be interpreted in light of levels that require an accurate determination of the behavioural domain that the test measures and not just looking at the performance of an individual compared to the performance of his group as is the case in standard-reference tests (Allam, 2011).

Standard reference tests compare the performance of an individual with the performance of his peers, while the benchmark tests compare performance to a specific performance level, without reference to the performance of other individuals, the purpose of standard reference tests is to facilitate comparison between individuals in the field that the test measures. As for spoken-reference tests, it is to evaluate the performance of the individual in the light of specific competencies (AL, Dosari, 1999).

This type of test has been associated with a contemporary approach to assessment, psychological and educational assessment called the Item Response Theory IRT.

It aimed to get rid of the shortcomings of the classical theory, and in this way it is possible to get rid of the criticisms that were directed at the classical theory of analogy referred to in (Hambleton & Swaminathan, 1985), the most important of which are: The psychometric properties of the test are determined for a group of individuals, and that the characteristics of individuals can be determined through the use of a specific test and not in absolute terms, and it assumes that the standard error is equal for all individuals as it does not indicate the extent of their achievement according to the item level only, but rather on the test as a whole (Rogers, Hambleton & Swaminathan, 1999).

Advantages of spoken-reference tests:

1. The purpose of the semantic reference tests is not to evaluate the performance of the student individually and follow the curriculum only, but also to the educational evaluation at higher levels, for example when evaluating the performance of the school as a whole and also in selecting students for graduate studies (Wikstrom, 2005).
2. Spoken-reference tests depend mainly on determining a set of desired educational outcomes and their specific levels of achievement, because this type of test is useful when educational institutions differ in providing different contents for their students, as it requires institutions that students must reach specific levels of mastery in acquiring specific information and skills (Wiberg, 2004).
3. The benefit of the reference-spoken tests is an assessment of the students' current achievement status, and also helps in determining the reasons for students' lack of mastery of some of the goals on which these tests are based and describing the appropriate methods for treating cases of failure to achieve the goals, as indicated by Block that most educational measurement experts and psychologists emphasize the preference of spoken-word tests in measuring the results of the educational process directly (Al-Anzi, 2004).
4. The term criterion does not necessarily refer to complete mastery on the characteristic continuum, rather the spoken levels can be identified at any point, and this point will be a specific behavior used to describe specific tasks that the student must be able to perform and the comparison is made in light of these levels, and these can also be changed Levels from period to period according to student growth (Abdul Salam, 1996).
5. The concept of spoken tests was associated with the introduction of educational measurement and evaluation, called the Item Repose Theory I R T, as this theory came to overcome many of the shortcomings of the classical theory, and it provided reliable methods in dealing with basic issues in educational measurement and evaluation, such as calibrating items, building question banks, and building spoken tests (Hambleton & Swaminathan, 1985).

Therefore, the item response theory contributes to solving problems that the classical theory could not solve, such as adaptive measurement, question banks in its new concept, and independent capacity estimates of those subjected to the sample of items they were exposed to, the independence of measurement is the essential difference between the classical theory and the item response theory, which Lord (1980) puts in the characteristic of invariance (Rup & Zumbo, 2006).

Among the basic assumptions on which the paragraph response theory is based and identified by (Hambleton & Swaminathan, 1985, Hambleton & Jones, 1993) and referred to in Al-Sherifin 2006 are as follows:

It implies that there is one ability that explains Unidimensionality:

1. One-dimensional assumption
The individual's performance on the test for this is called one-dimensional models. (Local Independence).
2. Assumption of positional independence.
It means that the individual's response to a certain item does not affect positively or negatively his response to any other item, and this indicates that the responses of individuals to the test items are statistically independent.
3. Assuming Item Characteristic Curve
The item characteristics curve is a mathematical function that links the probability of a correct answer for paragraph P ($\emptyset$) and the subject capacity ($\emptyset$) measured by a set of items in the test that was constructed.
4. Speededness
That is, the subjects who fail to answer the test items fail because of their limited ability and not because of insufficient time to reach and answer the item.

The item response theory includes several models, the most important of which are:

1. One-parameter logistic- model
The one-parameter model is one of the simplest and most popular models of response theory to items, expressed by the mathematical function that relates the probability of a respondent's correct answer to the item.

Item difficulty parameter and item characteristic curves that differ only in their position on the attribute continuum, and this model assumes equal power for all items, which is equal to (one true) and that the guessing parameter is equal to zero for all items, and the mathematical function that represents probability is expressed in the following equation Hambleton & Swaminathan, 1985):

$$P_i(\theta) = \frac{e^{D(\theta-b_i)}}{1 + e^{D(\theta-b_i)}} \quad , \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$$

Whereas:

θ : the probability of a correct answer for an individual whose ability θ

(D) Scaling Factor equals (1.7)

θ = Individual capacity.

b_i : the difficulty parameter of paragraph i

a_i : Paragraph highlighting parameter

This model depends on the difference between the ability (θ) represented by the respondent from the letter (S) in the characteristic to be assessed (the ability behind the subject's answer, and the degree of the item (i) that the respondent wants to answer, which is represented by the symbol (b_i)) (Al Taqi, 2009).

Figure (1) indicates the curves of three items, whose function (logarithmic) and includes only one parameter to represent the differences between items is the difficulty of the item (b_i) Item Difficulty Parameter, in turn, it represents the ability of the individual when the probability of the correct answer on the item = (0.5) i.e. ($P(\theta) = 0.5$), that is, the difficulty of the item is the value whose probability of answering any of the items = (0.5). (Crocker and Aljina, 2009).

Figure 1: Characteristic

2. Two - parameter logistic model

This model assumes

that the guess for all items is equal to zero and its parameters are more difficult than the parameterized single model. This model is expressed by the following equation:

$$P_i(\theta_j) = \frac{e^{Da_i(\theta_j-b_i)}}{1 + e^{Da_i(\theta_j-b_i)}} \quad , \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$$

The steepness of the curve increases with increasing the value of (a_i); The tendencies of the curves are not equal and intersect because the parameter of discrimination is variable for each item in this model, (Lord, 1980: 125) and Figure No. (2) shows that.

Figure (2): Two

Where a_i : paragraph highlighting parameter

3. Three - parameter logistic model

It is based on three parameters: Difficulty, Discrimination, and Guess. What distinguishes this model from the two-parameter model is that it added the parameter of guesswork, and this equation expresses this model:

$$P_i(\theta_j) = c_i + (1 - c_i) \frac{e^{Da_i(\theta_j - bi)}}{1 + e^{Da_i(\theta_j - bi)}}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$$

Figure (3) shows the characteristic curve of the three-feature model function, and the three parameters, the parameter of the estimation c) show the height of the asymptote below the curve, and the parameter b)) which represents the level of difficulty of the item at the point of inflection of the curve, that is, when the probability of getting the correct answer = $c + 1/2$;

The parameter for the strength of item discrimination (a) is the slope of the curve at its inflection point and represents the variance of the response level on the item with the power level. (Lord, 1980: p.125; Toland, 2008: p. (11).

Figure (3): Item Characteristic Curve in the Three Parameter Model (Lord, 1980: 124)

From the above, it is evident the great progress made by the modern theory of measurement in the liberation from the effect of the characteristics of individuals on the parameters of the items, and from the effect of the features of the items on the characteristics of individuals when building tests, and the numerous studies that have been conducted on that.

Bani Atta (2019) conducted a study entitled “The effect of the characteristics of the item and the level of individuals' ability to assume positional independence in the item response theory.” It aimed to investigate the effect of the characteristics of the item and the level of individuals' ability to assume local independence, and to achieve the goal of the study, responses of (1000) individuals were generated on (100) items, and analysing it using the two-parameter logistic model to find the parameters of the items and the ability of individuals, four models of tests were formed according to the level of difficulty and discrimination of the item, and the individuals were divided into three levels according to ability, the results of the study showed that the percentage of vertebrae pairs violating the assumption of positional independence was the highest in the case of the first model (difficult vertebrae and high discrimination) at the high capacity level and lowest at the low power level, the results also indicated that the percentage of vertebrae pairs violating the postural independence assumption was increasing with the increase in the ability level in the first model, while it was less in the fourth model (easy item and low discrimination), the results showed in general that the characteristics of the item and the level of ability of individuals had an effect on the assumption of local independence and that the distinction of the item had a greater role in influencing it than the difficulty of the item by testing the significance of the statistical differences between the proportions of the pairs of vertebrae violating the assumption of positional independence by individuals' ability level and test model. As for the study of al-Balawi and Abd al-Aal (2018), its aim was to reveal the effect of the test time on the estimates of the parameters of the item according to the item response theory and the classical theory: Where an achievement test of the multiple-choice type was built (28) items of the mathematics course, and three pictures were formed for the test that differed in the response time, it was applied to a sample of (451) students, and then the data were analyzed using (ITEMAN, (BILOG-MG3) program). The results showed an agreement of item response theory and the classical theory: There were statistically significant differences ($\alpha=0.05$) in the averages of estimating discrimination features due to time in favor of the appropriate time (30 minutes), and the presence of statistically significant differences in the accuracy of estimating the difficulty parameters and the discrimination parameters in favour of the second image (the appropriate time 30 d), as it is the most accurate in estimating these parameters according to the item response theory, the results of the M-statistic tests for differences between the reliability coefficients calculated by traditional methods also showed that there are statistically significant differences in the reliability factors in

favour of the second image (30d) and that the percentage of agreement between the two theories in sorting the item based on the parameters of difficulty and distinction in the first image is 89% and the second image is 96% and the third image is 68%.

As for Al-Nasraween (2019), the aim of his study was to show the effect of the number of alternatives in the multiple-choice test on the item information function and the test according to the triple model parameterized within the framework of the item response theory, the aim of the study was verified by building a multiple-choice achievement test in the second part of the mathematics subject for tenth grade students in government schools in the capital governorate, the final image of the test consisted of (38) items, and the researcher prepared three samples of the test, differing in the number of alternatives for its items only. The study sample consisted of (1530) students from the tenth grade, and the study found statistically significant differences in the reliability in favour of the five-alternate model and the four-alternate model, as the results showed that there were no statistically significant differences between the arithmetic means of the information function due to the variable number of alternatives for the item. Among the studies concerned with the spoken reference test, the aim of Al-Mutairi's study (2018) was to build a criterion reference test to measure the research efficiency and skill of students of the College of Education using the item response theory. Where the narrated news of the reference was built, its items revolved around several areas related to scientific research such as types of research according to the method and design, elements of research, sources of information for educational research, variables, types of samples, educational research tools, psychometric characteristics of educational research, and statistics, the test, consisting of (40) items, was applied to a sample of (362) male and female students from the College of Education at Kuwait University and the College of Basic Education in the State of Kuwait. Through the use of the single model, the study reached a test consisting of (37) items to measure research skills, as it has validity through its conformity with the hypotheses of the Rush model in addition to having a high degree of stability for both the difficulty of the item and the ability of the individual.

The aim of Al-Shehri (2018) study was to use the one-parameter logistic model (Rush model) in constructing a spoken-reference test to measure mathematical competencies in engineering thinking, an achievement test was prepared that measures the levels and abilities of engineering thinking, consisting of (38) items of the multiple choice type, the study sample consisted of (480) students from the middle third grade in Al-Jawf governorate, the results showed that the assumptions of the one-parameter logistic model were fulfilled and (38) items matched, and two items that did not match the model were deleted. The results also showed that items were within the criteria of multiple criteria in the theoretical literature for measurement, and the results showed for the estimates of the study sample individuals excluding (3) individuals who do not match the model. The ability parameters of the study sample ranged from (-1.389) to (1.674).

Afolabi's (2015) study aimed to determine whether it is possible to use the spoken-language mathematical aptitude test for the eighth grade of primary school to predict student behavior in higher school, the study used the quantitative approach with a correlative design, to determine whether there are relationships between selected variables and the grades of the students on the semantic test and the variables tested are success in the mathematics course for eighth-grade students, staying in the ninth grade and success in the Georgia test for high school graduation from high school, the study population consisted of a small rural school located in the city of Georgia, and the study sample was selected from recent high school students of the school, whose number is (300), and (120) students were selected to participate in the study. The study data were analyzed using statistical analysis methods. The results of the study showed a strong positive relationship between students' scores on the reference spoken mathematical aptitude test and students' success in a mathematics course or subject in the ninth grade. The results of the study also showed a positive relationship between students' scores on the reference spoken mathematical aptitude test and their success in the Georgia test for graduation from high school, the results of this study reinforce the need to find appropriate predictions or indicators to predict future behaviour of students. The results of the study showed the need to do this as soon as possible to reduce the risk of students dropping out of high school.

The Study Problem

There has been a clear interest by researchers in item response theory recently, as it attracted the attention of test workers and was used in designing various types of tests, mental and achievement scales, and attitude scales.

And through the experience of the researcher's teaching to undergraduate students at Al-Isra University, it was clear that there is a lack of consistent standards based on accurate objective scientific methods in evaluating students' performance.

Based on that, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent are the assumptions of the item response theory fulfilled in the current study data according to the three-parameter model?
2. How well do individuals' responses match the three-parameter model?

3. What evaluated the estimates of the three parameters of the test items (difficulty, discrimination, guessing) of test item according to the three-parameter logistic model of item response theory?

Significance of the Study

1. Examine the assumptions of the item response theory in relation to clarifying the effect of the subjects' characteristics and the items on the accuracy of the assessment of the subjects' parameters and the items.
2. This study uses the logarithmic three-parameter model in developing spoken-reference tests to highlight the interest in this type of test in different subjects.

The Study Terms

Criterion-referenced test: This type of test is used to evaluate an individual's performance in relation to a criterion (absolute level of performance) without the need to compare his performance with that of other individuals (Allam, 2011).

Al-Ajili defines it (2005): "The test in which the student's level is determined in relation to a fixed criterion (level) without reference to the performance of others, and this level is usually related to the behavioural goals of the subject."

It is defined procedurally: a set of multiple-choice items with four alternatives and one correct only prepared according to the assumptions of the item response theory and analysing the results of students' responses using the taught triple model to achieve the accuracy and objectivity of measuring student achievement.

Item Response Theory: One of the modern theories in psychological and educational measurement in which the relationship between the performance of the respondent and the underlying characteristic of the subject of the measurement is determined according to a specific mathematical function, this theory is based on a number of models called latent trait models by which the performance on the vertebral is linked to the ability of the responder (Hambleton & Swaminathan, 1985).

Achievement test: A structured procedure that measures the level of students' performance of subject-matter information and skills by answering a set of paragraphs that include the content of the academic subject (Odeh, 2001).

Al-Abadi (2006) defines it as "a set of vocabulary (questions) that are given to the student to answer them verbally or in writing, and it may be objective, essay, drawings or forms used for comparison and measurement."

The limits of the study

- Spatial limit: This study is limited to students of the Department of Psychology at Al-Isra University.
- Time limit: This study was conducted in the second semester of the academic year 2020/2021.
- Objective limit: The results of this study were confined to the achievement test spoken for in the psychometric course prepared by the researcher.

Study methodology and procedures

The Study Population

This community consists of all students of the Department of Psychology, Faculty of Arts, Al-Isra University / Jordan.

The Study Sample

The study sample consisted of all (115) students of the Department of Psychology for the academic year 2020/2021.

The Study Tool

In order to achieve the aim of the study, a spoken-reference test was constructed in the psychometric course according to the following steps:

1. Determining the content: the content was determined to identify the basic items to be achieved in the teaching of the psychometric course and the vocabulary includes: The concept of measurement and its importance, levels of measurement and their characteristics, types of psychological tests and measures, statistics in psychological and educational measurement, measures of central tendency, measures of dispersion, types of test criteria, psychometric properties of tests, intelligence tests, personality tests and measures, tendencies tests.
2. Formulating the behavioural goals that were covered by the topics and expected to be mastered by the students.

3. A specification table has been prepared for the test to relate content to goal levels.
4. (41) items of the multiple-choice type with four alternatives and one correct answer were formulated, taking into account the conditions for building this type of test item and their conformity with the behavioral goal that they measure in terms of content and cognitive level.

Validity of the tool

To ensure the content validity, the researcher presented the 41 test items with a list of behavioural objectives, content, and a table of specifications to a number of experts and specialists in measurement and evaluation at the university, in order to ensure the validity of the test in terms of scientific accuracy and to achieve the research objectives, the researcher relied on the opinions of experts and referees, in light of this, the researcher made a number of amendments to a number of test items by deleting, adding and amending until their number became (36) valid items to achieve the research objectives, as each item obtained an acceptance rate (85%) of the experts' opinions, and the test items were promised ready for application to the exploratory sample, thus achieving the apparent and content validity (Al-Batsh and Abu Zina, 2007). The global validity of the test data was calculated using Principal component analysis and computing the Eigen value, and noting the Explained Variance for each of the factors.

Test Reliability

The reliability coefficient was calculated on the experimental sample estimates to verify the reliability of the scale, as the reliability of the internal consistency was calculated according to the Cronbach Alpha equation, and the half-segmentation, the results of which are shown in Table (1).

Table 1: The internal consistency factor of the scale paragraphs:

Alpha coefficient	Retail midterm
0.91	0.94

It is evident from Table (1) that the alpha stability coefficient for the scale as a whole reached (0.91) and the half partition stability coefficient for the test was 0.94, and both values were high and considered acceptable values in educational studies, indicating that the test has a high degree in measuring the characteristic.

Presentation and discussion of results:

First: the results related to the first question:

The text of the question: "To what extent are the assumptions of item response theory fulfilled in the current study data according to the three-parameter model?"

A- Unidimensionality assumption

The factor analysis was calculated for the final test data related to the answers of (115) male and female students for (36) items using spss statistical programming, where the analysis produced (13) factors, the first factor of them (13.908%) was explained by the variance, and all the factors (64.740%) of the total variance were explained. Table (2) shows the values of the complete root and the ratio of the explained variance for each factor, as well as the cumulative interpreted variance ratio.

Table 2: The results related to the global analysis of the response of (115) students to the test in its final form (36) items

Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues				Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings				Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total		
1	5.007	13.908	13.908	5.007	13.908	13.908	3.242		
2	2.314	6.427	20.336	2.314	6.427	20.336	2.005		
3	1.924	5.346	25.681	1.924	5.346	25.681	1.855		
4	1.838	5.104	30.786	1.838	5.104	30.786	1.842		
5	1.800	5.000	35.785	1.800	5.000	35.785	1.722		
6	1.613	4.481	40.267	1.613	4.481	40.267	1.707		
7	1.470	4.082	44.349	1.470	4.082	44.349	1.662		
8	1.405	3.903	48.252	1.405	3.903	48.252	1.652		
9	1.327	3.687	51.939	1.327	3.687	51.939	1.631		

10	1.259	3.497	55.436	1.259	3.497	55.436	1.602
11	1.173	3.259	58.695	1.173	3.259	58.695	1.540
12	1.145	3.180	61.875	1.145	3.180	61.875	1.493
13	1.032	2.865	64.740	1.032	2.865	64.740	1.354
14	.991	2.752	67.492				
15	.963	2.675	70.167				
16	.895	2.486	72.653				
17	.870	2.416	75.069				
18	.821	2.281	77.350				
19	.722	2.007	79.356				
20	.719	1.997	81.353				
21	.675	1.874	83.227				
22	.622	1.728	84.956				
23	.585	1.624	86.579				
24	.544	1.512	88.092				
25	.517	1.435	89.526				
26	.472	1.311	90.838				
27	.465	1.293	92.130				
28	.434	1.206	93.336				
29	.403	1.120	94.456				
30	.390	1.083	95.539				
31	.353	.982	96.520				
32	.301	.837	97.357				
33	.281	.781	98.138				
34	.259	.719	98.857				
35	.219	.610	99.467				
36	.192	.533	100.000				

It can be seen from Table (2) that the value of the latent root of the first factor is 5.007 and explains 13.908% of the total variance, the value of the result of dividing the first potential root by the second latent root was 2.164, and since this ratio is greater than (2), this is an indication that the first factor is a dominant factor, and this confirms the unidimensional assumption. These two indicators indicate the fulfillment of a one-dimensional assumption of the test in its final form, meaning that the test measures a single feature. The one-dimensional assumption is reinforced by the representation of latent roots using a (Scree Plot).

B-Local Independence Assumption

Since the one-dimensional assumption is fulfilled, this indicates that the assumption of local independence is fulfilled, because the one-dimensional assumption is equivalent to the assumption of local independence.

C- Speediness assumption

The students took the sufficient time to answer the items of the test, and the researcher did not receive any notes about the lack of time during the application of the test, this is an indication and evidence that students' failure to answer the test items is due to their low abilities and not to the effect of the speed factor.

Second: Results related to the second question: The text of the question on "To what extent do the individuals' responses correspond to the three-parameter model?"

The data of the study sample (115) male and female students were entered for the (36) items of the final exam on the Bilog-MG3 program. The results of the analysis showed that all the responses of the individuals were identical to the model except for (5) students, where the Chi-Square values were statistically significant at the level of $\alpha \leq 0.05$. Using the same program, the analysis was re-analysed again to see the extent to which the test items of the model were met. Through the results of the Chi-Square at the significance level $\alpha \leq 0.05$, it was found that two items with numbers (14 and 23) were not identical, where the probability value was less than 0.05. Table (3) Evaluate these indicators.

Table 3: Chi-square values and significance level for the three-Parameters Logistic Model

N	Chi-square for good matching	Sig	N	Chi-square for good matching	Sig
1	12.4	0.089	19	5.3	0.503
2	21.15	0.141	20	19.6	0.266
3	6.8	0.453	21	3.8	0.209
4	18.5	0.366	22	16.7	0.076
5	4.7	0.583	23	13.00	0.000
6	9.2	0.120	24	12.89	0.078
7	12.16	0.096	25	12.3	0.418
8	11.79	0.108	26	24.4	0.097
9	9.7	0.289	27	11.2	0.294
10	4.1	0.765	28	14.3	0.167
11	5.3	0.503	29	14.00	0.066
12	11.6	0.755	30	5.9	0.752
13	12.7	0.896	31	6.3	0.504
14	17.8	0.001	32	4.6	0.332
15	7.8	0.449	33	10.3	0.157
16	3.8	0.961	34	14.11	0.904
17	10.9	0.528	35	7.6	0.187
18	8.7	0.189	36	7.3	0.426

Through Table (3), the Chi-Square value and its statistical significance are shown at the significance level $\alpha \leq 0.05$, and it is found that (34) test items out of the total items (36) are not statistically significant, and this indicates their conformity to the logarithmic three-parameter model.

Third: The results of the third question: The text of the question on "What are the values of the estimates of the parameters of the test items (difficulty, discrimination, guessing) for the test item according to the 3-parameter logistic model of item response theory?"

To answer this question, the parameters of the paragraph (difficulty, discrimination, and estimation) and the standard error were found using the Bilog-MG3 software. Table No. (4) shows the evaluation of these estimates for the test items in their final form (34) items (after deleting the non-conforming items).

Table 4: Evaluate the parameters of the items and the standard error of the test in its final form according to the three-parameter model.

N	Difficulty parameter	Standard error of the difficulty parameter	Discrimination parameter	Standard error of the discrimination parameter	Guess parameter	Standard error of the guessing parameter	N	Difficulty parameter	Standard error of the difficulty parameter	Discrimination parameter	Standard error of the discrimination parameter	Guess parameter	Standard error of the guessing parameter
1	-0.132	0.030	1.655	0.226	0.154	0.048	18	1.006	0.153	0.899	0.137	0.421	0.061

2	0.424	0.023	0.769	0.120	0.227	0.037	19	0.781	0.147	0.482	0.058	0.243	0.083
3	1.330	0.104	1.184	0.234	0.206	0.024	20	1.691	0.566	0.880	0.141	0.323	0.040
4	0.167	0.258	0.658	0.089	0.138	0.060	21	0.682	0.114	1.052	0.169	0.203	0.035
5	1.412	0.121	0.891	0.243	0.241	0.026	22	0.363	0.279	0.759	0.084	0.213	0.074
6	-0.822	0.218	0.610	0.146	0.210	0.041	24	0.977	0.110	0.891	0.136	0.221	0.033
7	0.861	0.190	0.879	0.170	0.208	0.021	25	-0.881	0.177	1.180	0.104	0.254	0.084
8	0.669	0.167	1.883	0.294	0.188	0.041	26	-1.290	0.126	1.211	0.413	0.207	0.064
9	0.682	0.256	0.933	0.238	0.256	0.047	27	-0.716	0.091	0.892	0.147	0.239	0.035
10	-0.601	0.074	1.635	0.161	0.252	0.051	28	1.515	0.125	1.254	0.271	0.251	0.025
11	-0.985	0.264	0.480	0.072	0.242	0.031	29	-0.159	0.082	0.892	0.207	0.219	0.020
12	0.188	0.082	1.272	0.433	0.413	0.025	30	0.646	0.239	0.784	0.198	0.311	0.041
13	-0.974	0.099	1.361	0.191	0.167	0.047	31	-0.834	0.156	1.119	0.180	0.195	0.034
15	0.750	0.418	1.549	0.185	0.172	0.050	32	1.144	0.240	0.793	0.147	0.202	0.039
16	0.648	0.205	1.827	0.173	0.312	0.051	33	-1.360	0.072	0.841	0.166	0.187	0.072
17	1.032	0.109	0.960	0.117	0.217	0.062	34	1.514	0.126	1.257	0.274	0.258	0.023

It is clear from Table (4) that the values of the difficulty parameter ranged between (-1.36 and 1.691), with an arithmetic mean of (0.304), the value of the standard error of the difficulty parameter ranged between (0.023 and 0.566), the value of the discrimination parameter ranged between (0.48 and 1.883), with an arithmetic mean of 1.054125, and the standard error of the discrimination parameter ranged between (0.058 and 0.433), as for the estimation parameter, its values ranged between (0.138 and 0.421), with an arithmetic mean of (0.235938), The standard error of the estimation parameter was between (0.02 and 0.084), Ree (1983) confirmed that the typical values of the discrimination parameter according to the logarithmic three-parameter model range between (0.5 and 2.5) and with an arithmetic mean (1). According to Hambleton (1989), the logarithmic three-parameter model has consistency when the values of the difficulty parameter range between (-2 and 2), the discrimination parameter ranges between (0.4 and 2), and the guessing parameter ranges between (0 and 0.25).

Recommendations

Through the results related to this study, the researcher recommended the following:

1. The possibility of using the test, which was built by the researcher and in its final form, to measure students' achievement in the subject of psychometrics for students of the Department of Psychology, because it has acceptable validity and reliability indications and is consistent with the requirements of the logarithmic three-parameter model.

2. Based on the methodology used in preparing tests for other courses and to ensure their psychometric properties.

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